

Research Article

Information Systems Security Issues and Preventive Measures

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Abstract: Information security, sometimes abbreviated as InfoSec, is the practice of protecting information by mitigating information risk. Typically, it involves preventing or reducing the likelihood of unauthorized or inappropriate access to data or unlawful use, disclosure, disruption, deletion, corruption, modification, verification, recording, or invalidation of information. This includes measures designed to reduce the adverse effects of such incidents. The primary focus of information security is the balanced protection of the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data, also known as CIA, with an emphasis on efficient policy implementation without compromising business productivity. Based on our research, Information security may be divided into three major categories network security, physical security and personnel security and there some issues will involve users are worldwide and can be used without limits.

Keywords: Security, Network, Malware, Threats, Vulnerabilities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The primary reason for 30 years of failure in the Information System Security industry stems from a failure to recognise one of the most fundamental security principles: no security solution is ultimately stronger than its weakest link. This notion, when combined with human nature and the inherent dynamics of the marketplace, has resulted in many of us in the business being forced to promote "fake cures" rather than actual answers.

Information security may be divided into three major categories: network security, physical security and personnel security. First, network security relates to the protection of the infrastructure utilized for data storage and transmission. This is generally accomplished through the use of technology and hardware such as intrusion detection systems (IDS), firewalls, routers, and so on. Antivirus software and rules for access control and authentication are examples of software.

Second, physical security relates to the protection of the building, work locations, gadgets, and data stored in the form of papers. This is accomplished mostly by access control devices such as security guards, ID cards and swipe cards, limited movement of media such as CDs, floppies, and documents,

and video monitoring such as fire safety. Physical controls monitor and govern the work environment and computer facilities. Doors, locks, heating and air conditioning, smoke and fire alarms, fire suppression systems, cameras, barricades, fencing, security guards, cable locks, and other devices are used to monitor and regulate access to and from such buildings. ("Information security - Wikipedia") ("Information security - Wikipedia") Physical controls include dividing the network and workplace into functional regions. Separation of tasks is an important physical control that is usually disregarded. It assures that an individual cannot perform a key task by himself. For example, an employee who files a reimbursement request should not be allowed to also authorise payment or print the cheque. An applications programmer should not also be the server or database administrator; these positions and responsibilities must be kept distinct.

Third, personnel security refers to preparations established to combat the possible threat posed by offshore vendor personnel. Background checks, such as reference checks and police checks, non-disclosure and confidentiality agreements, such as internet access policies and mobile computing rules, training and awareness, business continuity and disaster recovery are some of the security methods utilized. Refers to the procedures used to obtain information and deliver ongoing services in the event of an emergency. Data backups at remote sites, risk assessment and restoration methods, fire, link, and power exercises, and alternate site management are some of these practices.

This paper aims to look into the previous studies discussing the information systems security with special focus on the issues related to information systems security and the suggested solutions to cater the threats that often occur. It is organized into four sections; Section 1 is the introduction; Section 2 discusses information systems security issues; Section 3 explains about the information system security threats and preventive measure; Section 4 provides the conclusion of this study.

2. INFORMATION SYSTEMS SECURITY ISSUES

Information system security managers play a very important role in knowing about the assets of their organisations, the vulnerability of their information systems to different threats, and their potential damages. Each threat and vulnerability must be related to one or more of the assets requiring protection. Logical and physical assets can be grouped into five categories:

1. Information- Documented data or intellectual property used to meet the mission of an organization
2. Software- software applications and services that process, store or transmit information
3. Hardware- information technology physical devices considering their replacement costs
4. People- the people in an organization who possess skills, knowledge and experience that are difficult to replace
5. Systems- information systems that process and store information

The various units of value or metrics for the valuation of assets may be in use. The common metric is monetary, which is generally used for data that represents money where the threat is direct financial theft or fraud. Some assets are difficult to measure in absolute terms but can be measured in relative terms. The value of information can be measured as a fraction or percentage of total budgets, assets, or the worth of a business in a relative manner. The impact of information security incidents may well be financial in the form of immediate costs and losses of assets. ("(PDF) INFORMATION

SYSTEMS SECURITY TRENDS & ITS IMPACT - ResearchGate"). There are few issues related to information systems security namely:

2.1 Downtime prevention

The importance of ensuring that digital networks used by companies for their revenue and operations are always available. Downtime refers to periods of time when a system is not operational which can result in financial losses and other negative impacts. To reduce downtime, companies can use several techniques including fault-tolerant computer systems that use hardware or software to detect hardware failures and automatically switch to backup systems. High-availability computing environments use backup servers, distribute processing among multiple servers and have high-capacity storage to recover quickly from a system crash. Recovery-oriented computing involves designing systems to recover quickly and implementing capabilities and tools to help operators pinpoint the sources of faults in multicomponent systems and easily correct their mistakes. ("Chapter 8 - Summary Management Information Systems") Disaster recovery planning and business continuity planning are also important to restore computing and communications services after they have been disrupted by an event such as earthquake, flood or terrorist attack. Business continuity planning focuses on how the company can restore business operations after a disaster strikes. Some companies outsource security functions to managed security service providers (mssps) that monitor network activity and perform vulnerability testing and intrusion detection. ("What are the most important tools and technologies for ... - HKT Consultant")

2.2 Network storage

The security vulnerabilities that arise when sensitive data is stored on remote servers maintained by third-party storage vendors. The cost of storage management is much higher than the initial acquisition costs. Most third-party storage vendors do not provide assurances of data confidentiality and integrity [CNN, 2006]. To protect the data, security systems should offer users assurances of data confidentiality and access pattern privacy. This ensures that the data remains encrypted throughout its lifetime on the server and is only decrypted by the client upon retrieval. (Gartner. ;1999)

2.3 Cell phone issue

The spread and impact of computer viruses and worms on cell phones through email attachments, internet downloads, mms attachments and Bluetooth transfers. The most common type of cell phone infection occurs when a phone downloads an infected file from a pc or the internet. Phone-to-phone viruses are on the rise, particularly those that infect phones running the Symbian operating system. One of the obstacles to mass infection is the large number of proprietary operating systems in the cell phone world. Cell phone virus writers have no windows-level market share to target, so any virus will only affect a small percentage of phones. ("Cell-phone Virus Basics - How Cell-phone Viruses Work - HowStuffWorks") ("Cell-phone Virus Basics - How Cell-phone Viruses Work - HowStuffWorks") Infected files often disguise themselves as applications like games, security patches, add-on functionalities and free stuff. Infected text messages may steal the subject line from a message received from a friend which increases the likelihood of opening it. (Radmilo Racic Et Al. ;2008)

2.4 Other issues

The security risks associated with cloud computing which is a technology that allows users to access and store data and applications over the internet instead of their own computers [Jonathan et.al, 2009]. Cloud computing has many benefits such as cost savings and increased flexibility but it also poses security risks because users do not have control over the hardware and infrastructure that their data is stored on. The only way to mitigate these risks is through contractual agreements with cloud providers. The current services level agreements (slas) and contracts offered by most cloud providers do not provide adequate coverage for the increased risks involved [Rana Gupta, 2008]. This means that companies and organizations need to carefully evaluate the security measures and contractual terms offered by cloud providers before deciding to use their services.

3. INFORMATION SYSTEMS SECURITY THREATS AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES

This section provides brief discussion on the information systems security threats by looking into the computer crimes and the possible preventive measures suggested by few studies. Many materials are talking about hacking of the systems.

A hacker is someone who attempts to obtain unauthorized access to a computer system. Crackers are often hackers with nefarious intentions. Hacker's spoof or misrepresent themselves by using bogus email accounts or impersonating someone else. Theft of products and services, system damage, and cyber vandalism, such as the purposeful interruption, defacement, or even destruction of a Web site or business information system, are all examples of hacker actions. Spoofing includes things like hiding the hacker's actual identity or email address, or diverting a Web link to a different website that benefits the hacker. Sniffing is an eavesdropping programme that analyses network traffic and can allow hackers to obtain private information transmitted across the network. DoS attacks, such as flooding a network or server with thousands of fake communications in order to crash or impair the network. A distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) assault employs hundreds or even thousands of machines to flood and overload the network from several ports of entry. Hackers can infect the PCs of thousands of unsuspecting users with malicious software, forming a botnet of resources for launching a DDoS attack. A zombie computer, often known as a bot, is a computer that may be used by a hacker to distribute spam or execute Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) assaults. When a victim executes seemingly harmless code, a link is established between their computer and the hacker's system. The hacker can then use the victim's computer to perpetrate crimes or disseminate spam in stealth. (B.Premkumar. ;2022)

In cyber security, hacking is the use of devices such as computers, smartphones, tablets, and networks to cause harm or corruption to systems, acquire information on users, steal data and documents, or disrupt data-related activity. A hacker is traditionally portrayed as a lone rogue programmer who is extremely competent in coding and changing computer software and hardware systems. However, this limited perspective does not address the underlying technical nature of hacking. Hackers are becoming more sophisticated, employing covert attack tactics meant to go undiscovered by cybersecurity software and IT professionals. They are also competent at developing attack vectors that dupe users into opening infected attachments or URLs and freely disclosing sensitive personal data.

In computer crime, the computer can be either the victim or the perpetrator. DoS assaults, virus introduction, service theft, and computer system interruption are the most economically devastating types of computer crime. Identity theft is another type of digital crime. An imposter collects critical personal information in order to impersonate another individual and gain credit, products, or phony

credentials. Phishing is the practice of creating phony websites or sending e-mail messages that look real in order to compel consumers into providing private information. Other phishing strategies include evil twins, which are wireless networks that masquerade as genuine Internet hotspots and are used to steal personal information, and pharming, which involves converting visitors to fake Websites that masquerade as valid Websites. Click fraud happens when a human or computer programme clicks on an internet advertisement without intending to learn more about the advertiser or make a transaction. Click fraud can also be committed using software programmes to click, and bot networks are frequently used for this reason.

3.1 Information Systems assets and threats

According to (Icove et al. ;1999) divided information threats into seven categories: software, hardware, data, network, physical, personnel, and administration, which includes security regulations and policies. Threats to IS assets are frequently categorised according to the type of assets involved. (Loch et al ;1992). A four-dimensional IS threat classification system was developed. Sources, perpetrators, intent, and consequences are Loch's four dimensions. The origins of threats to IS assets can come from within or outside the organisation, the attackers can be human or nonhuman, their activities can be unintentional or intentional, and the outcomes can include disclosure, modification, destruction, and denial of service. Posthumus (2004) also identified three primary dangers to company information security: risks from natural disasters, risks from technology, and risks from people. In their analysis of how businesses responded to IS threats, White et al. (1996) made a distinction between internal and external information security activities. On the basis of the NIST SP800-30 security standard, internal functions relate to technical difficulties whereas external functions deal to non-technical aspects, such as management and operation security (NIST, 2002).

All of the works mentioned above divide IS resources and related dangers into two categories: IT-related and non-IT-related. Software, hardware, data, and network threats are classified as IT-related, whereas people, administrative, and physical/environmental facilities hazards are classified as non-IT-related. According to (Icove, 1999) the main personnel challenges are technical training, user education regarding security obligations, and reporting processes for occurrences. The majority of a company's security policies and procedures are decided internally, according to Madnick (1978), in addition to externally sought requirements like privacy laws or governmental restrictions. In several recent research (Birch et al., 1992; Siegel et al., 2002; Gordon et al., 2003), it is recommended that administrative policies include risk transference and insurance.

Both IT- and non-IT-related factors need to be taken into account for information security to be effective (Madnick, 1978; Straub, 1990; Ines, 1994; Kankanhalli et al., 2003; Posthumus, 2004). Instead of being limited to individual products or systems, such security should be evaluated across the entire IT environment (Von Solms, 1996). Clear definitions of administrative regulations are necessary (Madnick, 1978; Ines, 1994; Siegel et al., 2002). Additionally, managers and users must both get training to make clear the rules and penalties for abusing IS (Straub, 1990; Goodhue and Straub, 1991; Thomson and von Solms, 1998).

3.2 Security countermeasures

According to Peltier (2001), a security countermeasure is a risk-mitigating measure that identifies, averts, or reduces loss from a particular IS danger or class of threats. According to Straub (1990), Straub and Nance (1990), Forcht (1994), Kankanhalli et al. (2003), it can be either preventive or a deterrent. According to Kankanhalli et al. (2003), advanced security software or controls, such as advanced access control, intrusion detection, firewalls, and surveillance mechanisms, are deployed as preventive measures to safeguard IS assets.

The creation of security policy statements and guidelines, training seasoned auditors to audit IS asset usage, educating users about what constitutes legitimate use of IS assets and the repercussions of illegal use of IS assets are all examples of deterrent measures. Businesses that incorporate preventative security software and deterrent administrative procedures into their security countermeasures dramatically lower levels of computer misuse (Straub 1990).

By putting non-IT countermeasures in place, internal error-related dangers could be significantly reduced. An information security policy offers management guidance and support for information security (BS7799-2, 2002), and it should be distributed to users throughout an organisation in a way that is pertinent to their work, easily available, and comprehensible (Fulford and Doherty, 2003). The IS security policy should also include general guidelines for dividing up security roles and duties inside a company. In addition to the core controls mentioned above, a security measure must stop violations of internal regulations, contractual responsibilities, and criminal and civil laws in order to be compliant with legal requirements. Risk-transferring controls are those that make an effort to transfer the risk to a different organisation, like a security service provider or an insurance.

Job description, resource allocation, and responding to security problems and malfunctions are typical countermeasures related to personnel security (BS7799-2, 2002). To limit human error and make sure users are aware of information security hazards and concerns, appropriate training and education for IS system processes and security courses are required (Straub and Welke, 1998). Additionally, both routine and irregular audits may help to reduce the possibility of facility abuse, fraud, or human theft (Vroom and von Solms, 2004).

4. CONCLUSION

Many of us in the industry are now driven to push "fake cures" rather than real solutions due to this idea, human nature, and the underlying dynamics of the market. Three main categories can be used to categorize information security: The first aspect of network security is the defense of the equipment used for data transmission and storage. Second, physical security deals with safeguarding the office, work areas, technology, and paper-based data. Most often, security guards, ID cards, swipe cards, the restricted movement of media like CDs, floppies, and documents, and video surveillance for things like fire safety are used as access control technologies. Third, personnel security describes measures put in place to counter the potential threat provided by employees of offshore vendors. Some of the security measures used include background checks, such as reference and police checks, non-disclosure and confidentiality agreements, internet access restrictions, mobile computing rules, training and awareness, business continuity, and disaster recovery. Refers to the processes used to supply continued services and collect information during an emergency.

Worms are autonomous computer programmes that independently replicate themselves across a network without the help of other programmes or data. Many worms make it their mission to detect the presence of debugging tools and modify or stop functioning. Information system security managers must be aware of the resources within their companies, as well as how vulnerable such systems are to various threats and potential harm. It is possible to utilize different measures or units of value for asset valuation. Information security incidents may have a financial impact in the form of out-of-pocket expenses and asset losses.

In conclusion, it is evident that the three categories of IS assets and threats—network, personnel, and regulation/legality—are insufficient as means of protecting businesses across all industries. Additionally, the majority of businesses in poor nations still rely only on technical solutions to tackle IS security-related issues, placing more emphasis on managerial controls than technical ones, which may portend future catastrophes. The findings are consistent with earlier research on small

enterprises (Keller et al., 2005; Gupta and Hammond, 2005). A security strategy should be created, and responsibility for it should be assigned, for organisations with lesser information threats, such as conventional manufacturing, distribution, or service companies or enterprises with minimal levels of computerization. Organisations that face significant information risks, on the other hand, should think about risk transference strategies to reduce financial losses and strengthen security related to regulations and the law.

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